

The Effects of Intravenous Hydration on Amniotic Fluid Volume and Pregnancy Outcomes in Women with Term Pregnancy and Oligohydramnios

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Abstract

Background: Oligohydramnios is a common obstetric complication in the third trimester, associated with adverse perinatal outcomes. Since amniotic fluid volume reflects fetal well-being, strategies to increase fluid levels are of clinical value. **Aim:** This study aimed to evaluate the effect of maternal intravenous hydration on amniotic fluid index (AFI) and pregnancy outcomes. **Methods:** A single-blind controlled clinical trial was conducted at Al-Imamein Al-Kadhimein Medical City, Baghdad, from April 2016 to March 2017. A total of 100 pregnant women with term gestation (37–41 weeks) and oligohydramnios (AFI ≤ 5 cm) were randomly assigned into two groups: intravenous hydration (n=50) and control (n=50). The intervention group received one liter of isotonic saline over 120 minutes. AFI was measured at baseline and re-assessed three hours later. Data were analyzed using paired and independent t-tests. **Results:** In the hydration group, mean AFI increased significantly from 4.10 ± 0.76 cm to 4.93 ± 0.81 cm ($p=0.0001$), representing a 20% rise. In the control group, AFI increased slightly from 4.17 ± 0.90 cm to 4.43 ± 0.90 cm, which was not statistically significant ($p=0.055$). Fetal distress occurred in 18% of the hydration group compared with 36% in controls, showing a significant reduction ($p=0.043$). All cases with fetal distress required cesarean delivery. **Conclusion:** Intravenous hydration is a simple, safe, and effective method to improve AFI in term pregnancies complicated by oligohydramnios. It may also reduce the incidence of fetal distress and the need for emergency cesarean section, making it a practical management option.

Keywords: Hydration, Oligohydramnios, Amniotic fluid index, Clinical trial.

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Introduction

Oligohydramnios, defined as a reduction in the quantity of amniotic fluid, represents a frequent obstetric complication during pregnancy, particularly in the third trimester. Its detection is

clinically significant because it has been associated with an increased risk of perinatal morbidity and mortality, warranting careful maternal and fetal evaluation (Copel, 2012; Torigian, & Ramchandani, 2016). Amniotic fluid

serves multiple essential roles in fetal growth and development, including cushioning against trauma, preventing cord compression, providing antibacterial protection, and acting as a reservoir of nutrients and growth factors (Underwood, Gilbert, & Sherman, 2005; Tong, et al., 2009). The assessment of amniotic fluid volume (AFV) is most reliably performed by ultrasonography, which is a safe and non-invasive technique widely used for monitoring pregnancy (Torigian, & Ramchandani, 2016). Quantitative indices such as the amniotic fluid index (AFI) and maximum vertical pocket (MVP) are commonly employed to semi-quantify AFV. Oligohydramnios is typically diagnosed when AFI is ≤ 5 cm or MVP ≤ 2 cm (American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists, 2012). The incidence ranges from 0.5% to more than 5%, depending on population and definition, with rates reaching 11% in post-term pregnancies (Rossi, & Prefumo, 2013). The regulation of AFV is dynamic and involves multiple fetal and maternal pathways, including fetal urination, swallowing, intramembranous transfer, pulmonary fluid secretion, and transmembranous flow (Moore, 2010; Nijland, & Ross, 1997; Modena, & Fieni, 2004). Disturbances in these mechanisms, whether from maternal disorders such as preeclampsia, chronic hypertension, or exposure to medications (ACE inhibitors, NSAIDs), placental abnormalities such as abruption or twin-twin transfusion, or fetal conditions such as growth restriction and congenital anomalies, can lead to oligohydramnios (McCurdy, & Seeds, 1993; Boix, et al., 2005). Clinically, oligohydramnios is of concern due to its strong association with adverse outcomes such as intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), low Apgar scores, meconium aspiration, fetal distress, and increased operative delivery (Kahkhaie, et al., 2014; Khuwaja, et al., 2016). Traditional management strategies include amnioinfusion, induction of labor, or expedited delivery, especially at term or when oligohydramnios coexists with other risk factors (Cunningham, et al., 2014; Hofmeyr, & Lawrie, 2012). However, these interventions may prolong labor, increase the risk of cesarean delivery, and raise the likelihood of neonatal

intensive care unit admission, without consistently improving outcomes (Moore, 2011). An emerging, less invasive approach is maternal hydration, which has been shown to transiently increase AFI in both normal pregnancies and those complicated by oligohydramnios (Patrelli, et al., 2012; Malhotra, & Deka, 2004). Both oral and intravenous hydration have demonstrated effectiveness, possibly through improved uteroplacental perfusion or altered maternal plasma osmolality leading to enhanced fetal urine production (Ross, Nijland, & Kullama, 1996). Given its safety profile and practicality, maternal hydration represents a promising adjunct in the management of oligohydramnios. The aim of this study was to evaluate the influence of intravenous hydration of mothers on amniotic fluid volume and in turn on pregnancy outcomes.

Method

This single-blind controlled clinical trial was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at Al-Imamein Al-Kadhimein Medical City, Baghdad, Iraq, over a 12-month period from April 2016 to March 2017. Eligible women were informed about the study objectives and procedures, and verbal consent was obtained before enrollment, consistent with ethical practices for interventional obstetric research (Manning, Platt, & Sipos, 1980). A total of 100 pregnant women with oligohydramnios, defined as an amniotic fluid index (AFI) ≤ 5 cm (American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists, 2012), and gestational age between 37 and 41 weeks (based on last menstrual period and confirmed by ultrasound) were included. Participants were randomly assigned into two groups of 50 each by a sealed-card method: Group A (intravenous hydration) and Group B (control). Randomization by sealed envelopes is an established approach for minimizing selection bias in clinical trials (Nageotte, et al., 1994).

Inclusion criteria were singleton pregnancy, cephalic presentation, intact membranes, normally situated placenta, and AFI ≤ 5 cm at term.

Exclusion criteria included maternal comorbidities (hypertension, diabetes, renal,

respiratory, or cardiac disease), primigravida status, premature rupture of membranes, structural fetal anomalies, intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), multiple gestation, previous cesarean section, active labor, or evidence of fetal compromise on non-stress testing (McCurdy, & Seeds, 1993).

Baseline maternal evaluation included detailed history, abdominal and pelvic examination, and ultrasound to assess gestational age, anomalies, IUGR, and AFI. AFI was measured using the Phelan four-quadrant method with a 3.5 MHz transducer, performed by an experienced ultrasonographer blinded to group allocation (Phelan, et al., 1987). All women were asked to rest before scanning to minimize confounding effects of uteroplacental perfusion on AFV (Moore, 2010). The intervention group received 1 liter of isotonic saline intravenously over 120 minutes. AFI was re-measured one hour after hydration in both groups, following bladder emptying. Labor induction was initiated in all participants, and intrapartum monitoring was conducted by continuous fetal heart rate auscultation. **Statistical analysis** was performed using SPSS v24. Data were expressed as mean \pm SD, frequencies, and percentages.

Paired t-test was used for within-group AFI changes, independent t-test for between-group comparisons, and Chi-square or Fisher's exact test for categorical variables. A p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Table 1 shows that the **maternal age, parity, and gestational age distributions** were well-balanced between the intravenous hydration and control groups.

- The **mean maternal age** was almost identical (27.5 vs. 27.9 years, $p=0.736$), with most participants between 20–29 years in both groups.
- The **mean parity** was also comparable (2.5 vs. 2.8, $p=0.307$), with the majority being multiparous (para 2–4).
- Similarly, **gestational age** distribution did not differ significantly between the groups (38.8 vs. 38.9 weeks, $p=0.804$).

Overall, the baseline maternal characteristics were statistically similar, indicating that the randomization process was successful and both groups were comparable at the start of the study.

Table 2. Maternal Age, Parity, and Gestational Age Distribution

Variable	Category	IV Hydration (n=50)	Control (n=50)	P value
Maternal age (years)	20–24	19 (38.0%)	16 (32.0%)	0.736
	25–29	16 (32.0%)	17 (34.0%)	
	30–34	7 (14.0%)	12 (24.0%)	
	≥ 35	8 (16.0%)	5 (10.0%)	
Mean \pm SD (Range)		27.5 \pm 5.1 (20–39)	27.9 \pm 4.9 (20–39)	
Parity	Para 1	13 (26.0%)	14 (28.0%)	0.307
	Para 2–4	31 (62.0%)	29 (58.0%)	
	Para ≥ 5	6 (12.0%)	7 (14.0%)	
Mean \pm SD (Range)		2.5 \pm 1.4 (1–6)	2.8 \pm 1.5 (1–6)	
Gestational age (weeks)	37	9 (18.0%)	10 (20.0%)	0.804
	38	11 (22.0%)	10 (20.0%)	
	39	16 (32.0%)	14 (28.0%)	
	40	9 (18.0%)	7 (14.0%)	
	41	5 (10.0%)	9 (18.0%)	
Mean \pm SD (Range)		38.8 \pm 1.2 (37–41)	38.9 \pm 1.3 (37–41)	

Table 2 demonstrate the mode of delivery and antenatal care (ANC) during this pregnancy distribution in the intravenous hydration group and control group. Concerning the mode of delivery: 9 patients (18 %) of the intravenous

group and 18 patients (36 %) of the control group delivered by CS. 41 patients (82 %) of intravenous group and 32 patients (64 %) of the control group delivered vaginally respectively. The P value was (0.043) which is statistically

significant. As regards history of ANC during this pregnancy: 26 patients (52%) of intravenous group and 27 patients (54%) has positive history of ANC during pregnancy while 24 patients (48

%) of intravenous group and 23 patients (46%) of the control group has no ANC during this pregnancy. However, P value was (0.841) which is statistically not significant.

Table 2. Mode of Delivery and Antenatal Care (ANC)

Variable	Category	IV Hydration (n=50)	Control (n=50)	P value
Mode of delivery	Cesarean section	9 (18.0%)	18 (36.0%)	0.043*
	Vaginal delivery	41 (82.0%)	32 (64.0%)	
ANC	Yes	26 (52.0%)	27 (54.0%)	0.841
	No	24 (48.0%)	23 (46.0%)	

Table 3 clarify amniotic fluid index distribution & comparison before and after therapy in the intravenous hydration and control groups. Overall, amniotic fluid index shows a rise in both intravenous hydration and control groups but the increase is more significant in the former. AFI Mean \pm SD in the intravenous hydration group(pre-hydration) was 4.10 ± 0.76 while in control group 4.17 ± 0.90 with a p value (0.657) which is statistically non-significant using paired t-test comparing two independent means. While post hydration, AFI Mean \pm SD in the intravenous group 4.93 ± 0.81 and in the control group 4.43 ± 0.90 with p value (0.005) which considered to be significant (by using independent t-test). It is clearly evident that AFI

Mean \pm SD in the intravenous hydration group shows an incremental growth from 4.10 ± 0.76 cm to 4.93 ± 0.81 cm in pre- and post-hydration (mean difference 0.83 cm) which is statistically highly significant using paired t-test for comparison of the two dependent means (p value 0.0001). Meanwhile in the control group AFI Mean \pm SD slightly increases from 4.17 ± 0.90 cm to 4.43 ± 0.90 cm (mean difference 0.26 cm) which is statistically non-significant (p value 0.055) using paired t-test comparing the two dependent means. There was a 20% rise in amniotic fluid index (AFI) in the intravenous hydration group which was significantly greater than the 3.4% increase of the control group.

Table 3. Amniotic Fluid Index (AFI) Before and After Treatment

AFI Index	Category	IV Hydration (n=50)	Control (n=50)	P value
Pre-hydration	<2.5	1 (2.0%)	2 (4.0%)	0.657
	2.5–2.9	3 (6.0%)	4 (8.0%)	
	3.0–3.4	3 (6.0%)	4 (8.0%)	
	3.5–3.9	9 (18.0%)	5 (10.0%)	
	4.0–4.4	14 (28.0%)	10 (20.0%)	
	4.5–4.9	13 (26.0%)	14 (28.0%)	
	5.0	7 (14.0%)	11 (22.0%)	
	≥ 5.5	-	-	
	Mean \pm SD (Range)	4.10 ± 0.76 (1.5–5.0)	4.17 ± 0.90 (1.5–5.0)	
Post-hydration	<2.5	1 (2.0%)	2 (4.0%)	0.005*
	2.5–2.9	-	-	
	3.0–3.4	2 (4.0%)	7 (14.0%)	
	3.5–3.9	3 (6.0%)	2 (4.0%)	
	4.0–4.4	4 (8.0%)	9 (18.0%)	
	4.5–4.9	9 (18.0%)	9 (18.0%)	
	5.0–5.4	15 (30.0%)	19 (38.0%)	
	≥ 5.5	16 (32.0%)	2 (4.0%)	
	Mean \pm SD (Range)	4.93 ± 0.81 (2.2–6.0)	4.43 ± 0.90 (1.7–5.5)	

Table 4 represents neonatal outcome in IV group and control group. It can be seen that baby weight mean \pm SD in the IV group was 3082 ± 223 grams with a range of (2700-3500) grams while in the control group was (3096 ± 283) grams with a range of (2600-3500) grams. The difference was not significant (p value 0.784). There were 12 cases (24%) in the IV group with Apgar 1 less than 7 while 15 case (30%) in the control group. However, it considered statistically non-significant (p value 0.311). Regarding Apgar 5 all of the IV group had an Apgar ≥ 8 and in the control group 2 cases had Apgar 7 and the remaining are above this. There was no statistical difference between neither groups (p value 0.515). Fetal distress was

found in 9 cases (18%) in IV group and in 18 cases (36%) in the control group. The difference between both groups was significant (p value 0.043). Meconium staining of the amniotic fluid was observed in 12 cases (24%) of the IV group and 13 cases (26%) of the controls. The Chi-square statistical test results showed no significant statistical difference between the two groups (p value 0.871). Regarding gender distribution, 20 cases (40 %) delivered male baby and 30 cases (60%) delivered female baby in the intravenous group. In the control group :19 cases (38%) delivered male baby and 31 cases (62%) delivered a female baby. There was no statistical significant difference between both groups (p value 0.838).

Table 4. Neonatal Outcome in the IV Group and Control Group.

Variable	Category	IV Hydration (n=50)	Control (n=50)	P value
Birthweight (grams)	2500–2999	13 (26.0%)	17 (34.0%)	0.784
	3000–3499	33 (66.0%)	27 (54.0%)	
	≥ 3500	4 (8.0%)	6 (12.0%)	
	Mean \pm SD (Range)	3082 ± 223 (2700–3500)	3096 ± 283 (2600–3500)	
Apgar 1	Score 4	2 (4.0%)	5 (10.0%)	0.311
	Score 5	3 (6.0%)	5 (10.0%)	
	Score 6	7 (14.0%)	5 (10.0%)	
	Score 7	10 (20.0%)	16 (32.0%)	
	Score 8	18 (36.0%)	15 (30.0%)	
	Score 9	8 (16.0%)	4 (8.0%)	
	Score 10	2 (4.0%)	-	
Apgar 5	Score 7	-	2 (4.0%)	0.515
	Score 8	10 (20.0%)	8 (16.0%)	
	Score 9	10 (20.0%)	11 (22.0%)	
	Score 10	30 (60.0%)	29 (58.0%)	
Fetal distress	Yes	9 (18.0%)	18 (36.0%)	0.043*
	No	41 (82.0%)	32 (64.0%)	
Meconium	Yes	12 (24.0%)	13 (26.0%)	0.817
	No	38 (76.0%)	37 (74.0%)	
Gender	Male	20 (40.0%)	19 (38.0%)	0.838
	Female	30 (60.0%)	31 (62.0%)	

Note: * Significant difference between proportions using Pearson Chi-square test at 0.05; * Significant difference between two independent means using Student's t-test at 0.05

Discussion

This randomized controlled study assessed the effect of intravenous maternal hydration on amniotic fluid volume in term pregnancies complicated by oligohydramnios. The findings demonstrated that intravenous hydration

produced a significant rise in AFI compared with the control group, supporting the role of hydration as a safe and practical intervention. The increase in AFI observed in the hydration group may be attributed to acute maternal osmotic shifts that enhance uteroplacental perfusion and stimulate fetal urine production,

thereby contributing to fluid restoration within the amniotic cavity (Patrelli, et al., 2012; Malhotra, & Deka, 2004). Importantly, the technique required no specialized equipment and was not associated with adverse maternal or fetal outcomes. Our results are in agreement with Patrelli et al. (2012), who reported that intravenous hydration in women with oligohydramnios produced significant improvement in AF volume compared with non-hydrated controls (Patrelli, et al., 2012). Similarly, Malhotra et al. (2004) demonstrated that acute hydration increased AFI in both normal and low AF pregnancies, though the effect was transient and tended to normalize as maternal plasma osmolality was restored through antidiuretic hormone regulation (Malhotra, & Deka, 2004). Borges et al. (2011) further confirmed that hydration with isotonic solution and oral water intake increased AFI significantly, producing a 20% improvement compared to controls. Kahraman et al. (2013) also showed that maternal hydration combined with left lateral positioning accelerated the rise in AFI, highlighting the role of posture and hemodynamic changes in fluid regulation. Nevertheless, not all studies have reported consistent benefits. Yan-Rosenberg et al. (2007) concluded that hydration was no more effective than expectant management, attributing observed changes to fetal position, diurnal variations in AFV, and measurement variability. Doi et al. (1998) suggested that hypotonic solutions rather than isotonic fluids are more effective in increasing AFI, pointing to maternal osmotic pressure changes as the main mechanism. These discrepancies underline that while hydration is generally beneficial, its effect may depend on fluid type, timing, and patient characteristics. The clinical implications of oligohydramnios are substantial, as diminished AFV increases the risk of cord compression, fetal hypoxia, and intrauterine demise. In our trial, cesarean delivery for fetal distress occurred in 36% of the control group compared with only 18% of the hydration group, indicating a protective role of increased AFI. These findings are in line with Umer (2009) and Jandial et al. (2007), who observed higher rates of non-reassuring fetal heart patterns and operative

deliveries in women with oligohydramnios. Similarly, Kahkhaie et al. (2014) showed that cesarean delivery for fetal distress was significantly more common in pregnancies with $AFI \leq 5$ cm. The association between oligohydramnios and meconium-stained AF is controversial. In our study, meconium was observed in 26% of the control group and 24% of the hydration group, a non-significant difference. This is consistent with Rossi et al.'s (2013) meta-analysis, which found no differences in meconium staining or Apgar scores between oligohydramnios and control groups. Conversely, Chauhan et al. (1999) reported that oligohydramnios was associated with low Apgar scores at 5 minutes, suggesting greater neonatal compromise. Taken together, the evidence suggests that maternal intravenous hydration is a simple, safe, and effective intervention for increasing AFI in pregnancies complicated by isolated oligohydramnios. While its impact on neonatal outcomes such as Apgar scores and NICU admission remains debated, the observed reduction in fetal distress and cesarean deliveries highlights its potential clinical utility. Further large-scale studies are needed to clarify long-term benefits, determine optimal fluid regimens, and establish standardized guidelines for incorporating hydration into routine obstetric practice.

Conclusion

This study demonstrated that intravenous maternal hydration in pregnancies complicated by isolated oligohydramnios significantly improves amniotic fluid volume while reducing rates of cesarean delivery and fetal distress, without maternal adverse effects. Given its simplicity and safety, hydration can be considered a practical management option. However, larger studies across different gestational ages are needed to validate these findings, particularly in pregnancies before 35 weeks. Continuous intrapartum monitoring, optimal neonatal care, and further exploration of combined therapies such as hydration with desmopressin are also recommended. Alternative AFV assessment methods should be investigated for improved risk stratification.

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